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How States Invoke Human Rights to Justify Their (In)Actions

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Summary: How States Invoke Human Rights to Justify Their (In)Actions

States increasingly rely on the language of human rights to frame and legitimise their policy choices. This practice is not inherently problematic: limitations on rights often require justification, and human rights law itself has an inherently justificatory structure. Problems arise, however, when states rely on arguments that deviate from the established criteria for limiting or derogating from rights, or when human rights rhetoric is deployed selectively to obscure violations.

This report examines how states invoke human rights language to justify their actions or inactions, sometimes in ways that undermine human rights. Focusing on the Finnish legislative process, the report analyses case studies to develop a typology of problematic human rights justifications. The report contributes to existing scholarship on abusive constitutionalism and the appropriation of human rights by offering a framework for identifying and analysing such practices within ordinary democratic settings.

A key analytical distinction in the report is between legitimate and illegitimate human rights justifications. Legitimate justifications are grounded in the accepted legal framework governing human rights obligations, including the distinction between negative and positive obligations and the cumulative criteria for permissible limitations, such as legality, legitimate aim, necessity, proportionality, and respect for the essence of the right. Illegitimate justifications, by contrast, fail to comply with these criteria. Importantly, we do not treat every controversial or contested interpretation as illegitimate but acknowledge reasonable disagreement. Instead, we focus on patterns of argumentation that systematically distort rights in ways detrimental to their protective function.

Methodologically, the report analyses legislative proposals and parliamentary review in Finland, where the Constitutional Law Committee of the Parliament conducts *ex ante* constitutional review of government bills before they are passed. This institutional context provides a rich environment for observing how governments frame their legislative proposals and how such arguments are evaluated. The Finnish system is particularly suitable for this analysis because public authorities are constitutionally obliged to guarantee the observance of both fundamental and human rights pursuant to Section 22 of the Constitution of Finland, and international human rights treaties formally occupy a strong position within the domestic legal order. Yet, the domestic standard of rights protection is intended to ascend to a high level as the constitutional doctrine is that international human rights obligations binding upon Finland feature as a minimum standard of protection.

The report develops a typology of five categories of problematic human rights justifications. The first is misdefinition of the extent of obligations, which occurs when states exaggerate or minimise their duties, often by overstating positive obligations or downplaying non-derogable duties. This category involves distorting the scope or intensity of the state's human rights duties, including by overstating positive obligations at the expense of negative obligations. Conversely, states may downplay positive obligations by suggesting that minimal or alternative measures suffice to discharge their duties. In a proposed

COVID-19 temporary lockdown act,¹ the Finnish government invoked its positive obligations to protect the rights to life and health to justify extensive restrictions on freedom of movement and other rights. While the aim was legitimate, the Constitutional Law Committee held that the measures were disproportionate and not the least restrictive means available.² The government thus expanded the scope of its positive obligations in a manner that improperly overrode other rights, misdefining the balance required by human rights law.

The second is misdefinition of the scope of a right, which involves artificially narrowing or expanding the situations or persons covered by a right. In the lockdown proposal, exceptions to movement restrictions were granted only to persons in “established relationships,” excluding other close personal relationships. The Constitutional Law Committee criticised this reasoning for narrowing the right to respect for private and family life in a way inconsistent with constitutional law and ECtHR jurisprudence, arbitrarily redefining who falls within the scope of the right.

The third is misclassification of absolute rights, where non-derogable rights are treated as subject to limitation or balancing against state interests such as security. Enacted as an exceptive law, the Act on Temporary Measures to Combat Instrumentalised Migration³ allows Finland to refuse asylum applications at parts of its border under certain conditions. The preparatory works and parliamentary review openly acknowledged conflicts with constitutional and international human rights obligations, including the principle of non-refoulement. Nevertheless, the legislation was justified through arguments emphasising national security, limited temporal and geographical scope, and continued respect for rights elsewhere. In reviewing the Act, the Constitutional Law Committee accepted that the law conflicted with the principle of non-refoulement but suggested that such conflicts could be tolerated in light of serious threats to national security.⁴

The fourth type is misclassification of interests as rights, in which political or security interests are framed as human rights to legitimise restrictive measures. In the preparatory works of the instrumentalisation law, national security concerns and the functioning of state institutions were linked without clear doctrinal explanation to the right to personal security. This reframing elevated a state interest into a rights-based claim, allowing restrictions on asylum rights to be presented as fulfilling, rather than limiting, human rights obligations.

The fifth is vulnerabilization, whereby access to rights is conditioned on proving vulnerability, creating hierarchies of deservingness and excluding those who do not meet narrow criteria. Under the instrumentalisation law, for example, asylum seekers at the border would only gain access to normal procedures if border guards deemed them vulnerable or at risk of inhuman treatment. Rights protection

¹ Government Bill (HE) 39/2021 Hallituksen esitys eduskunnalle laiksi liikkumisvapauden ja lähikontaktien väliaikaisesta rajoittamisesta.

² Constitutional Law Committee statement PeVL 12/2021 vp – HE 39/2021 vp.

³ Government Bill (HE) 53/2024 Hallituksen esitys eduskunnalle laiksi väliaikaisista toimenpiteistä välineellistetyn maahantulon torjumiseksi.

⁴ Constitutional Law Committee statement PeVL 26/2024 vp – HE 53/2024 vp.

thus became dependent on an informal assessment of vulnerability, transforming vulnerability from a basis for enhanced protection into a gatekeeping tool for denying rights to others.

The report situates these Finnish examples within broader global trends of human rights misappropriation, drawing parallels with illiberal regimes that use human rights rhetoric to entrench power and undermine democratic norms. By offering a structured framework for analyzing human rights justifications, the report contributes to the theoretical understanding of how legal language can be strategically deployed to shield state behavior from scrutiny. The typology presented serves as a diagnostic tool for identifying argumentative distortions and enhancing accountability in rights-based governance.